

Drive for Unipolar BLDC Motor based on SEPIC Converter

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Abstract: Our suggestion is to employ a single ended primary inductance converter (SEPIC) as a front-end device to provide unipolar current to a permanent magnet brushless dc (BLDC) motor. In series with each phase, a switch is added. Their drive specs are a little easier to understand because all of the switches gate drives have ground references. Additionally, low voltage applications benefit from being able to increase the available input voltage to better control current. With the SEPIC converter sourced by an ac source, it is preferable to use the discontinuous conduction mode. At this operating mode the waveform of the line current is very close to that of the line voltage. We demonstrate that power factor is improved with reduced low order harmonics without the use of voltage and current sensors. The low cost and reduced number of components of the suggested topology makes it attractive for use in many types of variable speed drive applications. Using MATLAB/SIMULIK, the proposed topology is simulated and validated.

Keywords: BLDC, DC motor driving, AC supply, SEPIC converter, and unipolar

I. Introduction

Such motor of motor that is gaining popularity by leaps and bounds is a Brushless Direct Current motor. According to Apollo Bearing, BLDC motors are typically used in the industries of appliances, automobiles, aircraft, consumer goods, industrial automation equipment and instruments. The PSD of BLDC motors implies naturally their electronically commutated nature as opposed to brush commutated. Motors compared to BLDC motors, they excel in various aspects, including their speed-torque characteristics, responsiveness to dynamic changes, energy efficiency, quiet operation, and range of rotational speeds. For use in variable speed drives, brushless dc motors must be made in mass quantity at as much cost as possible low. Some examples include appliance, automobile, airplane, consumer product, healthcare, industrial automation and instrument applications.

Unlike BLDC motors, brushless DC (BLDC) motors use no brushes, are commutated electronically instead. Compared to all motors BLDC motors offer superior speed vs torque characteristics, excellent dynamic responsiveness, high efficiency, salient features of noiseless operation and large speed range at their respective RPMs. Cost reduction is the secret to getting brushless DC motors produced in big volumes and deployed in variable speed drives. The cost of the converter is reduced and variable speed drives can be employed in HVAC, fans, pumps and other appliances that are normally run with constant speed drives. Bipolar motors use a simpler circuit and require fewer electronic components but are normally operated by bipolar current and a six-switch inverter.

The use of unipolar driven motors is a consequence of the low cost. Fig. 1 shows the most basic unipolar drive, where a Zener diode in series with a single switch in series with each winding. The phases' stored energy has to be released therefore making this motor inefficient. C-dump converter shown in Figure 2 permit complete regeneration control and good performance. But it also comes with the downside that controlling the dump capacitor voltage is difficult and, if it did fail, could be fatal.

Fig 1: Three phase unipolar converter

Fig 2: BLDC C-dump converter

This is a prerequisite for the switching reluctance motor not to see negative torque spikes when phase current is turned off, while it isn't for BLDC motor. Then phase current overlaps during the switching intervals are allowed, leading to reduction of the commutation torque pulsations. This phenomenon is utilized in the design suggested in this work, which operates the dump capacitor at a lower voltage. For the ac supply operation case, a voltage balancing control scheme utilizing split capacitor and the change of the machine windings is required, but the converter is based on a unipolar BLDC motor with a three-switch converter.

A SEPIC (single ended primary inductance converter) functioning in DCM (discontinuous conduction mode) establishes the basis for this study. When doing so, the resultant average input current will be sinusoidal to a certain degree, though will not change with the changes in the input voltage, so as to maintain a constant duty cycle. This realization makes the control circuit simpler without any need to sense or control the input current. For this reason, this capability can be used to combine PFC stage and the inverter (output regulation) stage, lowering cost significantly. Fig. 3 displays the schematic of an ac motor drive consisting of an integrated inverter and PFC stage.

Fig 3: PFC stage and inverter integrated with AC Motor

II. Unipolar Excitation for BLDC Motors

Consequently, the waveforms depicted in Fig. 4(a) illustrate a current conduction phase and a torque generation phase at each specific moment. As illustrated in Figure 4(b), this phenomenon arises from unipolar current conduction, which results in phases characterized by a singular direction of current flow.

The continuous production of torque remains achievable; however, this is predicated on the premise that one phase consistently conducts current at a given moment. Naturally, an overlap in the conduction of phases can facilitate a more uniform torque output. The fundamental justification for the preference of unipolar excitation lies in the observation that the inverter component typically incurs higher expenses relative to the motor, thereby rendering it highly plausible to significantly reduce the cost of the inverter in comparison to both the drive and the aggregate expense. When we elect to utilize unipolar excitation, it becomes imperative to maintain an imbalance in the currents of one of the motor's phases, as this results in the phase currents no longer achieving equilibrium. Consequently, it is crucial to ensure that access to the motor's neutral point is secured.

Fig 4: (a) Excitation for bipolar (b) Excitation for unipolar

III. Model Proposed for Converters

Fig. 5 shows the converter characterized by four regulated diodes and switches. A SEPIC dc/dc converter is realized as the frontend configuration comprising switch S_1 , inductors L_1 and L_2 , diode D_1 and the intermediate capacitor C_1 and the output capacitor C_2 . In particular, the diode D_1 is located within the return path instead of the positive rail, somewhat deviating thus from standard SEPIC configuration. The critical role is prevented from having electrical flow with any phases that have a negative back emf.

The activation or deactivation of each of the three switches S_A , S_B , and S_C is governed by the electrical currents transverse the three windings of the machine, A, B and C. Since switching are allotted one for each phase, currents passing through them are inherently unidirectional. In particular, the diodes D_A , D_B and D_C facilitate freewheeling of winding currents during the off state of the switches, e.g. when the switch is in the off state in the context of current regulation and phase commutation. The extracted voltage is used to energize the three phases of the motor and regulate the current. The voltage across capacitor C_1 is used to deactivate the phases and effectuate their demagnetization.

Fig 5: BLDC motor drive based on SEPIC converter

IV. Operation based on AC Supply

For the application of this topology illustrated in figure 6, a high-power factor from a proposed topology is beneficial for applications that require operation from an alternating current supply. The theoretical power factor is equivalent, and the converter operates as a voltage follower, with the input current naturally tracking the input voltage profile. The voltage across the intermediate capacitor must exceed the phase back electromotive force during suitable phase demagnetization with a unipolar Brushless Direct Current (BLDC) motor load when the phases are in a saturated state. Near the zero crossings of the input voltage, the input current waveform is distorted. In this scenario the drive, which incurs no expenses in process, provides power factor which is both superior and favorable to that of the conventional circuit.

Fig 6: AC Supply connected to proposed converter

V. MATLAB Final Results

Simulation done through MATLAB SIMULINK based simulation has been done to prove that the proposed topology is efficient in terms of its operational efficiency. Figure 7 shows an illustrative block diagram which describes the implementation of the drive system. A triad of Hall effect sensors detects the rotor's position and from this the phase winding to be energized is then ascertained. Motor's velocity is derived from positional inputs and the reference speed is juxtaposed with the reference velocity. Modulation of phase currents is done in the aligned manner to the reference current using hysteresis control methodology. Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) control of switch \$S_1\$ provides for regulating the DC bus voltage. This load consists of a hysteretic brake that is affixed to the shaft of the motor and is operating as a motor.

Fig 7: Drive system block diagram

Using a PI controller, the reference and actual speeds are compared to create the current reference. It is evident that performance is enhanced by using the recommended architecture.

Fig 8 and 9: Before boosting DC output voltage and After boosting DC output voltage

Fig 10 and 11: Voltage waveform with DC error and Waveform with speed error

Fig 12 and 13: Waveform of rotor speed and EMF Ea waveform

VI. Conclusion

The new converter topology for unipolar excitation of brushless DC motors as proposed is based on a SEPIC converter operating in DCM. The following advantages are offered by the proposed scheme. The presently proposed converter has four grounded referenced switches. Moreover, their gate drive circuitry is also less complicated because of the relatively low cost and small size. This enables the system to withstand the upper end of the current regulated operation range of the drive, providing the network either a boost or buck capability of the input dc voltage. Because the input current tends to track the input voltage, high-frequency harmonics of a low order and high-power factor is produced. It eliminates the realistic possibility of shoot-through defects, which arise from the use of bipolar converters.

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